

2nd
ANNUAL
REPORT

*for the
period ending
June 30, 1958*

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, Inc.

Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st-
1956/57-
Washington.

v. 23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

Z673.C96A15

020.624

58-915 rev

Library of Congress

2nd

ANNUAL REPORT

for the period ending June 30, 1958

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

1025 CONNECTICUT AVENUE, N.W., WASHINGTON, D. C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Members of the Council and Members of the Board of Directors

DOUGLAS M. BLACK

President, Doubleday & Company, Inc.

LYMAN H. BUTTERFIELD

*Editor-in-Chief, Adams Papers
Massachusetts Historical Society*

GILBERT W. CHAPMAN

President, The Yale & Towne Manufacturing Co.

VERNER W. CLAPP

President, Council on Library Resources, Inc.

FREDERICK HARD

President, Scripps College

BARNABY C. KEENEY

President, Brown University

JOSEPH C. MORRIS

Vice-President, Tulane University

JOHN M. SCHIFF*

Partner, Kuhn, Loeb & Company

FREDERICK H. WAGMAN

*Director of the University Library
University of Michigan*

WARREN WEAVER

*Vice-President for the Natural and Medical Sciences
The Rockefeller Foundation*

HERMAN B. WELLS

President, Indiana University

LOUIS B. WRIGHT

Director, Folger Shakespeare Library

* Through August 20, 1958. Mr. Schiff was succeeded on November 12, 1958, by Mr. Whitney North Seymour, *Partner*, Simpson Thacher & Bartlett.

COMMITTEES AND OFFICERS

Executive Committee

GILBERT W. CHAPMAN, *Chairman*
VERNER W. CLAPP
BARNABY C. KEENEY
FREDERICK H. WAGMAN*
LOUIS B. WRIGHT

Finance Committee

JOHN M. SCHIFF, *Chairman***
GILBERT W. CHAPMAN

Officers

GILBERT W. CHAPMAN
Chairman
LOUIS B. WRIGHT
Vice-Chairman
VERNER W. CLAPP
President
MELVILLE J. RUGGLES
Vice-President
ELIZABETH OAKES
Treasurer
MELVILLE J. RUGGLES
Secretary
Assistant Treasurer

* Through November 12, 1958. Dr. Weaver has succeeded Dr. Wagman as a member of the Executive Committee.

** Through August 20, 1958. Mr. Schiff was succeeded by Mr. Seymour on November 12, 1958, and Mr. Clapp was named to the Committee at that time.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in 1956 in the District of Columbia, having as its principal objective "to aid in the solution of library problems; to conduct research in, develop and demonstrate new techniques and methods and to disseminate through any means the results thereof." The Council was established at the instance of the Ford Foundation which has made it a grant of \$5 million to be expended over a five-year period.

The Council, whose members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C. It conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals.

THE SECOND YEAR

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., came into being on September 18, 1956, the date of its first meeting. Its first annual report, for the fiscal year ending June 30, 1957, was for a period of approximately nine and a half months. The present report, for the fiscal year ending June 30, 1958, is thus the first for a full twelve-month period.

During this period the Council appropriated sums totaling \$403,361 for the support of thirty-two new projects, covering many aspects of library work. At the same time it continued its efforts toward defining its program so as to assure the most useful application of the resources entrusted to it.

“THE PROBLEMS OF LIBRARIES”

Under this heading in the Council's first annual report attention was called to some of the factors which must shape a program directed, as is that of the Council, to the solution of library problems. Library work is conducted through institutions. Each institution's primary needs—for buildings, books and staff with which to operate—constitute for it the basic and continuing problems. But in developed countries today these problems connected with the maintenance and extension of library work in present forms are accepted as community responsibilities. It is, then, to other than problems of local need to which the program of the Council is addressed—to problems which cannot simply be solved by additional expenditures, by “more of the same.” What are these problems?

In the words of an aphorism probably as old as Melvil Dewey, father of modern American library science, it is the purpose of library work to “get the right book into

the hands of the right reader at the right time." This statement of objective has served the libraries in the United States well through the years. Toward the execution of this purpose the library world has put to use—and created when necessary—an imposing panoply of arrangements with which the individual librarian is enabled not only to exploit his own resources but to supplement these with the resources of other institutions. To an incipient degree, indeed, any library, no matter how small, can as a result of such arrangements command the resources of the world. These arrangements make use, in the first place, of those bibliographical devices through which the identity and location of a wanted book is made known—catalogs and announcements, bibliographies and reviews, indexes and abstracting services, the results of cataloging and classification, guides to collections, union catalogs and union lists, and the like. They include in the second place those arrangements through which a work, once identified, is brought to the reader—programs of library acquisition, storage and preservation; provisions for lending, photocopying and other services. So extensive is this array that separate guides are often needed even to its individual parts; there are thus special compilations dealing with national bibliographies, the indexes to periodical literature, lists of government documents, the literature of various subjects such as chemistry, and even directories of photocopying services. So elaborate are some of these arrangements—like those affecting national union catalogs, the orderly acquisition of foreign publications or the preservation of newspapers in microcopy—that they have required years of cooperative effort and the expenditure of great sums to organize and set going.

In the light of these more recent developments it is perhaps now possible to rephrase the objective of library

work in terms differing somewhat from the aphorism quoted above. Such a rephrasing might read as follows: The objective of library work is to be able to provide the reader, no matter where he may be, with information as to what recorded knowledge exists applicable to his interest, and to be able to furnish him with the relevant portion of that record, no matter where it may be located.

If this be the purpose of library work, then it is obvious that a number of problems must be solved before it can be fully realized. It is also apparent that these are the very problems which prevent even the greatest of existing libraries from fully executing their tasks, for they are faced with problems unforeseen by Melvil Dewey and unmanageable by the techniques known to him—problems springing from the staggering increase in the rate of publication and in the tempo of research.

In general these problems fall into three categories. The first comprises that class of problems which stem from the inadequacies of the means of *bibliographic access*. Involved are devices, procedures and facilities through which a recorded source of information is identified and located. Catalogs, bibliographies, indexes and finding aids of all kinds—including the aids for ascertaining what relevant finding aids exist—are all involved. The second category consists of problems arising from deficiencies in the means of *physical access*—the arrangements through which a record, having been identified, is made available so as to be placed under the reader's eye. Acquisition, storage and arrangements of books, interlibrary lending, and photocopying are here involved. The third category may be defined as *administrative arrangements* and involves such factors as library organization, government and financing, recruitment and training for librarianship, development of standards, interlibrary cooperation, and the like.

A number of the projects encouraged by the Council during the past year have fallen into each of these categories; still other projects have come under *planning and fact-finding*. The projects are best described under the headings which these categories suggest.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC ACCESS

The heart of the library problem is in the *record* of recorded information. As an ancient writer said of the catalog of the Alexandrian library, it is the thread of Ariadne through the labyrinth. A modern librarian, John Cotton Dana, thinking of another aspect of the same problem, referred to the utility of the "library without books," implying that a most useful library can exist without a stock of books but that no library can be useful without some means of bibliographic access. The thesis might indeed be maintained that libraries make a greater contribution through their catalogs than through their actual acquisitions, for the latter are useless without the former, and, while no library can have all books within its walls, yet through suitable records it can command for its users all books wherever they may be.

The *record* when developed should be as simple as possible, but it should be adequate. It should be comprehensive when needed, be selective when needed; be current or be retrospective when and as needed by the reader. The problem is to make this record, which includes bibliographies, catalogs, indices and similar works, adequate in terms of physical media, cost to the library and satisfaction to the inquiring reader.

Standardization

One of the major areas of bibliographic activity which still—even after all that has been done—offers large possibilities of improvement is that of the cataloging of publications. As long ago as 1850 Charles C. Jewett, the librarian of the Smithsonian Institution, demonstrated a plan (based on the storage and re-use of stereotype plates) by which individual libraries might make use of the cataloging information and apparatus prepared at the cost of others. Jewett's plan failed because of the imperfect technology of his day, and his dream was not realized until 1901, when the Library of Congress began to sell its catalog cards at a price fixed by the mere cost of reproduction. The benefits which have flowed from this service have been immeasurable, and have not been limited just to the inexpensive duplication of cataloging records, important though that be; they have made it possible for any library, no matter how small or how newly formed, to make use of a master plan constructed for the organization of the collections of one of the greatest of all libraries.

This was possible only because the Library of Congress and the libraries which use its services share the same standards.

If it is obvious that there are efficiencies to be gained (both in saving of expense and in improved service) by sharing of expert cataloging service within a country, it would also appear that there are similar potential gains as between countries. Is it not absurd that a major part of the cataloging effort of the principal American libraries must go into cataloging of foreign books which have presumably already been cataloged in the countries of origin? Should it not be possible for American libraries, for example, to make use of the cataloging product at

least of the English-speaking—not to mention other—countries?

A condition precedent to such a situation is the sharing of standards. It was with this in mind that the Council's first grant was to the American Library Association to enable it to be represented at the meeting of the **German Library Association** (Verein Deutscher Bibliothekare), in Lübeck in June 1957, as a first step toward bringing the differing cataloging systems of Central Europe and of other countries closer together. At this meeting the Verein's cataloging committee voted to recommend abandonment of the rules for filing which have long differentiated German use from that of French and English-speaking countries.

The Council has made three other grants in this area during the past year. One was for a meeting to plan the next steps toward **the international coordination of cataloging rules**. In this meeting the American library groups having responsibility for current efforts in catalog code revision agreed to defer to the leadership of the International Federation of Library Associations. The Federation had appointed in 1954 a Working Group on the Coordination of Cataloging Principles, the chairman of which is currently Mr. Frank C. Francis, C.B., Keeper, Department of Printed Books, British Museum. Mr. Francis's group had performed some useful preliminary studies looking to the elimination of national differences in cataloging practice, and it was to expand the scope of the group's work that the Council's next grant was directed. This was to enable the Federation, through the group, to prepare for the convening of an international conference on coordination of cataloging principles to be held in 1960 or 1961. The immediate application of the grant is toward the expense of a preliminary planning

meeting, to be held in the summer of 1959 in London. In a third grant in this same connection, the Council made it possible for the American Library Association to invite Mr. A. H. Chaplin, Deputy Keeper, Department of Printed Books, British Museum, and Dr. Ludwig Sickmann, Dozent am Bibliothekar-Lehrinstitut des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen, Köln-Lindenthal, dual executive secretaries of the IFLA group, to attend an institute of catalog code revision sponsored by the Association at Stanford University in June 1958.

The Council has also sought to encourage the development of a cataloging standard for a geographical area where no such standard now exists. There has been no generally accepted cataloging code in Iran, and no generally accepted rules for cataloging Persian publications in Western libraries. In libraries outside of Iran such publications are cataloged according to local rules, which among other things results in many different representations of an individual author's name. Correspondingly, this means within Iran a lack of the basic standards which have been found in other countries essential to the effective organization of library resources. As a result of two grants to Dr. Nasser Sharify, Deputy Parliamentary Librarian of Iran on leave, a code for cataloging Persian books has been developed and will be published by the American Library Association. It is anticipated that this publication, which carries to a new field certain standards which already enjoy wide application, may in time encourage the development of norms having a similar basis of wide acceptability where none now exist.

Mechanization

The high cost of cataloging and indexing and of the publication of catalogs and indexes and other bibliographical tools in the face of the ever increasing quantity of materials pouring into the libraries today makes increased mechanization of the tools of bibliographic access a necessity. The time for hand-written catalog cards is as much past as hand-written books. The problem is to make bibliographic access more prompt, more nearly complete, more responsive to inquiry.

The *Current List of Medical Literature*, published by the National Library of Medicine, is at present the largest indexing service—in terms of quantity of material indexed—of the literature of a special subject published anywhere in the world. In 1957 it listed more than a hundred thousand articles in the field of medicine and provided half a million index entries to these articles. The ten monthly issues of the *Current List* total each year approximately 3500 pages. There are in addition two semi-annual cumulative indexes of approximately 800 pages each. The *Current List* provides medical research with the most prompt and comprehensive record of activity in the field at present available. Nevertheless, it has severe deficiencies. That it indexes only about half of the published literature in medicine is one; that a considerable lag occurs every six months due to the recurrent absorption of manpower by the semi-annual indices is another.

The National Library of Medicine, with the aid of a grant from the Council on Library Resources, has started a two-year project for the improvement of the *Current List* through the application of automatic information-handling equipment. It is proposed to mechanize the

indexing and the preparation of the printer's copy of the *Current List* in such a manner as to avoid much of the present manual processing. To this end it has projected experiments with punched-tape-operated typewriters, punched-card-operated cameras, and other devices. An objective is to increase the coverage to nearly one hundred per cent of the world's periodical medical literature—estimated at perhaps 200,000 articles per year. Among other objectives are improvements in ease of use and in legibility, improvements of the indices and their method of compilation, and segregation, if and when needed, of references to the literature of specialties within the medical field.

The National Library of Medicine has undertaken to report for the use of others on its experience. It is hoped that the improvements effected through mechanization in *The Current List of Medical Literature* may be adaptable to other indexing services.

“Telereference” is a name, coined by the Council, to designate a system for consulting card catalogs by television. If feasible, it might make possible the elimination, and thus the cost, of departmental and branch library catalogs in university, public library and other systems. It might make all the catalogs in an area such as New York City interconsultable. It might as a third possibility allow all the libraries of an area to pool their cataloging efforts into a single regional catalog. Telereference is technologically feasible; the question is as to the economies of its application. In a study performed for the Council by the Operations Research Department, Engineering Research Institute of the University of Michigan, it was found that it would cost approximately \$258,000 to install telereference in the many libraries of the University of Michigan campus, which served as a test case.

Maintenance of the system at Michigan would cost \$25,000 per annum, while the savings over present operating costs would amount to only about \$10,000. It is obvious, in view of this, that further development of less expensive equipment is necessary before telereference becomes practical. An interesting byproduct of the study was the statistical analysis of the queuing problems that would be met in any attempt to transfer the use of divisional catalogs to the central catalog through tele-reference devices. This analysis had to take into account such factors as peaks of use, both in divisional libraries and system-wide, and "holding time" (duration of searches in the catalog). A report on the study has been published by the Engineering Research Institute.

The preparation of catalog cards is a mechanical operation which combines aspects of both mass production and individual or piecemeal handling. Typically, this operation consists in mass producing as many copies of the basic or "unit" card as will be needed for the various entries in the appropriate catalogs. Thereafter, individual copies of these cards are "written up" by typing on their upper margins the additional entries under which they are to be filed.

This system is obviously not efficient. The total number of cards is usually small from a mass production point of view—ten to a hundred cards, while the "writing up" must always, except in the very largest systems, be done one card at a time.

Under these circumstances it has appeared useful to develop a device which would in one operation reproduce the "unit card" and at the same time perform the "writing up." To do this a camera (dubbed "the cataloger's camera") was projected which would reproduce the "unit card" by a self-perfecting process involving no

delay for laboratory development. The camera should also, however, have a second optical system, through which the filing entries printed at the bottom of the "unit card" might be transferred to the upper margins of individual cards during the process of reproduction.

The Council has given two purchase orders to the Radio Corporation of America for development of such a camera. A design plan for the camera, which is proposed to be of such a size that it can be operated by the cataloger at his desk, has been completed, and a working model illustrating the principles of operation and characteristics of the product is now under construction.

Coordination of Effort

There is no doubt that improvement of the means of bibliographic access is to be sought through standardization and mechanization. But the experience of the library world is that the greatest gains of all are to be sought through coordination of effort—through systematic and cooperative enterprises in which the accomplishment of one is made to serve the needs of all through skillful organization of the flow of work.

Bibliography begins with the book, and the physical book begins with the publisher. If the effort of publisher and librarian could be coordinated toward the simultaneous solution of the problems of bibliographic and physical access, this might be one of the most important achievements to which the Council could contribute.

By "cataloging in source" is meant the inclusion of cataloging information regarding a particular book in the book itself at the time of printing. Such a system, were it in general effect, would achieve the ultimate goal for which systems of cooperative and centralized cataloging have been devised over a period of more than a

century: it would bring a standardized catalog entry, created by the effort of one competent agency, together with the book wherever the two are needed together.

Libraries, of course, constitute a principal place where the book and the catalog entry are needed together, and much waste motion is now expended in effecting this. If this waste motion could be reduced, not only would books reach the shelves faster, but funds might be released for purchase of additional books. But there are other circumstances also in which conjunction of the standardized bibliographic description and the book to which it applies can be of use. An author, about to cite a work under his eye, is often puzzled how to describe a book with a perplexing title-page. "Cataloging in source" would provide him with the description under which the book will be found in libraries by those who wish to pursue his sources. "Cataloging in source" would similarly provide a source of identical and standardized entry for all vehicles of bibliographic information—for publishers' and booksellers' catalogs, trade lists and bibliographies. Since the "cataloging in source" entry would provide subject-entries and shelf-classification notation derived from recognized systems, this information could be used not only by private collectors of books to organize their collections, but potentially also by booksellers in arranging their stock. Indeed, it has been suggested that the classification symbol could be used as a sort of telegraphic code in the book trade to avoid both lengthy descriptions and misunderstandings in the citation of books, and also in warehousing.

Desirable as it may be, however, let it not be supposed that "cataloging in source" is something easy to accomplish. No book can be adequately cataloged until it is—at the very least—in the final stages of manufacture, and this from the publisher's point of view is the worst time

of all to incur any delay, no matter how brief, for purposes of cataloging. From the point of view of the agency doing the cataloging, the urgency created by the publisher's situation, as well as by the necessarily unfinished state of the book, provides far from the ideal circumstances for its own work. Yet the advantages to be derived from the system, if successful, are so great that it was deemed necessary to make the attempt.

Early in January 1958 the Librarian of Congress, Mr. L. Quincy Mumford, with the assistance of a small grant from the Council, asked Dr. Andrew D. Osborn, Associate Librarian of Harvard University, to make a study of the feasibility of initiating a system of "cataloging in source." After consultation with a number of publishers, and after inquiry into the potential usefulness of the system, Dr. Osborn, sceptical at first, became convinced of the practicality as well as the importance of the proposal. His report, rendered the beginning of March 1958, urged a demonstration.

Despite the substantial effects which the success of "cataloging in source" might have on the catalog card distribution program of the Library of Congress, Mr. Mumford accepted Dr. Osborn's recommendation and the Council in mid May made a second grant to enable the Library to carry it out. A demonstration of the practicability of the proposed system was planned by Mr. John W. Cronin, the director of the Library's Processing Department, whose career has been devoted to the development of centralized cataloging services for the benefit of libraries and intellectual workers everywhere. This demonstration involves the cataloging by the Library of Congress, prior to publication, of approximately a thousand books during the next six to twelve months. In order to test the various factors involved, cooperation will be sought from as many publishers as

possible. Simultaneously, a study will be conducted to ascertain the effects of the experiment upon the operations of libraries. Before the end of the year more than two hundred publishers had agreed to participate in the experiment.

In another step to encourage coordination of effort, the Council has given support to the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc., of Springfield, Missouri. The grant is specifically for use in demonstration of a **cooperative effort in centralized processing of books**, including cataloging and preparation for the shelves. Ten small to medium independent public libraries, situated at distances of up to 250 miles from each other and serving twelve counties with a population of approximately 250,000 persons, had established the Service in May 1957. On October 1, 1957, ten days after the Council made its grant, which was specifically to purchase equipment, an eleventh library joined the non profit cooperative.

Although centralized processing is rather commonplace within university, county and municipal library systems, this is the first effort of this nature among small institutions responsible to separate jurisdictions and entirely independent of each other. The experiment commenced well. During the first nine months of operation the project processed 23,526 items at a cost of forty cents each, considerably less than the average cost for processing items in individual libraries. The librarians of the principal library involved estimate that the operation has saved it alone more than three thousand dollars during the first year.

Well begun is half done. A condition of the Council's grant was that records should be made available for use in a technical and economic evaluation of the project. To further this, the Council has made a small grant to

the American Library Association to enable it to evaluate the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc., experience for the benefit of the library profession generally. The application of the grant is toward the expenses of a study by Mrs. Brigitte L. Kinney, a student at the Graduate Library School, University of Chicago, in which Mrs. Orcena Mahoney, the Executive Secretary of the Association's Resources and Technical Services Division, is participating. It is hoped that the results of this study, to be ready early in 1959, may prove of value to other libraries seeking similar solutions to their processing problems.

Bibliographies

The past thirty years have witnessed numerous applications of the techniques of microfilming, photostating and similar processes to the reproduction of historical source materials. These techniques make it possible to bring together in photographic form in one place authentic copies of materials whose originals are scattered in many depositories and even in many countries. Numerous partial guides to this material exist, but much of it is not generally known or useful, inviting duplication of the effort which produced it. Among the efforts to control this material bibliographically have been the *Union List of Microfilms*, published by the Philadelphia Bibliographical Center, the Microfilm Clearing House maintained at the Library of Congress, and such special lists as *Newspapers on Microfilm*, originally prepared by the Library of Congress for the Association of Research Libraries.

To assemble the information regarding this material (including also a guide to the various guides) in a single *vade mecum* which can display to the historical scholar

the wealth of material of this kind now available to him, the Council has made a grant to the American Historical Association. This will make it possible for the Association, which has named Dr. Richard W. Hale as the editor, to compile **The Guide to Photocopied Historical Material in the United States and Canada**. Other, non Council, funds are available for publication. The project, which also has Canadian sponsorship, is expected to be completed in the fall of 1959.

An aspect of the project worthy of notice is the intention of the editor to provide a manual of information about the application of photographic techniques to historical studies, the equipment used, and the bibliographic consequences. In the course of the work, too, use is being made of photographic and other duplicating mechanisms which promise to demonstrate new and more efficient methods of handling bodies of bibliographic data.

PHYSICAL ACCESS

Rax Me That Buik, "Reach Me That Book," is the imperative used as the motto of the Scottish Central Library. It suggests, in short, that it is of limited value to know that a book of potential usefulness exists, if it cannot be brought within reach.

Libraries are, of course, the institutional expression of the need to have books within reach. When Benjamin Franklin and his friends in 1731 pooled their separate book resources to form the Library Company of Philadelphia, "the Mother of all the N. American Subscription Libraries," their action did not increase the number of books available to them, but it did bring those books within easier reach. Libraries in America have been extending the process ever since. The Farmington Plan

for the Acquisition of Foreign Publications, the United States Book Exchange, and numerous other arrangements and devices have been adopted in the interest of physical access.

Acquisition and Distribution

When the United States entered World War II it needed information of all kinds about other portions of the world. The country's great research libraries, it was found, had each been acquiring the foreign publications adjudged "most important," and there was consequently a crippling lack of those publications of less than greatest but still of great importance. From this discovery sprang the Farmington Plan. Some sixty American libraries by cooperative effort share responsibility for acquisition of foreign publications within certain categories having potential usefulness for research. The peacetime responsibilities of the United States have given the program added significance. The Plan has now been in effect for more than ten years. Its execution has been burdensome on those who participate in it. It has certain obvious defects: it has brought in some material of less than first rate quality; it has omitted some material having that attribute; it overlooks many categories of publication, including serials and government publications; it is not world-wide. Accordingly, in response to the need to ascertain whether the Plan has in fact brought to the country the publications it was intended to bring, whether those publications are generally accessible to researchers, whether the mechanisms of the Plan need revision, and whether its scope should be reduced or broadened, the Council has given support to a survey and an evaluation of the operation of the Plan by a grant to Princeton University on behalf of the Association of

Research Libraries. The Association's Farmington Plan Committee, headed by Dr. Robert B. Downs, Director of the University of Illinois Library, is supervising the survey, which is being conducted by Mr. Robert Vosper, Director, and Mr. Robert L. Talmadge, Associate Director, of Libraries of the University of Kansas. The results of their evaluation will be reported as the basis for action on the Plan at a full meeting of the Association in January 1959.

Like the Farmington Plan, the **United States Book Exchange, Inc.**, has been in existence for more than a decade, and a survey of this independent, non-profit organization's effectiveness is much needed. The USBE draws its representation from the American Council on Education, American Council of Learned Societies, Engineers Joint Council, Library of Congress, National Research Council, Smithsonian Institution and Social Science Research Council, as well as from the organizations represented in the Council of National Library Associations. Its purpose is to serve as a center for the exchange of duplicates of books and periodicals having potential value for research, but not having sufficient market value to make them profitable to the antiquarian book trade. Its stock includes more than three million items occupying more than twelve miles of shelf space. In 1956 it served 1,323 institutions, about half of which were American and the remainder foreign, and placed 386,468 publications. It thus performs a service which the book trade cannot adequately perform for materials of this sort. Yet the economics of the operation are not clear. Under a grant from the Council, a study is being made of the basis of operation and method of executing the program, looking to the possible redefinition of its activities, and to possibilities and bases of future expansion and financing. The study is being made by

Mr. Edwin E. Williams, Associate Librarian for Book Selection, Harvard University Library.

Within any one region, if taken sufficiently broadly, there usually may be found a considerable resource of library materials. A particular region may for example contain a university library, a state library, several large public libraries, one or more college libraries and a number of small public libraries. It may now be asked: What informational services can legitimately and reasonably be expected of the publicly supported libraries within the area by the public of the area? What precedents exist for **organizing the library resources of the region** to serve the entire needs of the region? What are the legal, administrative, bibliographic and communications apparatus requisite for coordination of such services? These are some of the questions that need to be answered before public library reference services can be coordinated, can be marshaled to respond to the needs of an era. To secure this information the Council has sponsored a study of the possibilities for regional coordination by Dr. Harry J. Krould, of Silver Spring, Maryland, a consultant with a wide background in political science as well as in reference work.

Copying Techniques

Copying is inseparable from the library. In fact, libraries exist on the basis of copies, for the printed book is but a copy of the author's manuscript, and in turn their contents may be copied whenever the reader finds information of sufficient importance to require exactitude in its use. Hence libraries are full of mechanisms for making copies—printing presses, wax-stencil, dye-process, lithographic and other duplicators; photostat, microfilm, and other photographic devices; not to mention

electrical data processing machines, typewriters, rubber stamps, pens and pencils. No book is of any use until a copy can be put in someone's hands. As libraries exist upon copying, it follows that any improvement in copying has potential value for libraries.

Books do not naturally lie flat. Copying them photographically in consequence involves a process of forcing them into a flat position punctuated by turning of the pages. This operation is performed manually. The costs of this manual operation are absorbed without complaint in the instance of microfilming only because other costs are low. If, however, copying were needed to serve really high-rental equipment such as television or telefacsimile, this cost, and the delay of manual page-turning, might become a limiting cost factor. Indeed, the inadequacy of available page-turning equipment has already been found to be limiting in the case of the interlibrary televising of book materials in the University of Virginia project described in the preceding *Annual Report*. **But an automatic book-cradle/page-turner** which would avoid crushing the spine of the book, yet make it possible for the camera to see into the inside margins, and which would at the same time obviate manual page-turning, could considerably increase the efficiency of present book-copying methods, *e.g.*, by full scale copying or microfilming. An initial step required the preparation of a design plan for such a mechanism, and the Council has for this purpose given purchase orders to the Radio Corporation of America and to The de Florez Company, Inc.

In another area of copying work, the electrostatic ink-cloud copying process, if perfected, offers considerable promise for library processes. The Council has commissioned a demonstration model of a **card-copying machine** embodying this principle from Mr. W. C. Huebner, a well known inventor in the graphic arts field.

Microphotographic Techniques

Microphotography has now been actively employed in the service of libraries and their users for several decades. Like many techniques invented to solve old problems, however, it has created perhaps fully as many problems as it has solved. For example, though microfilm is widely used to provide a permanent copy in place of the impermanent original form of the newspaper, it has been found that microcopies are themselves subject to deterioration. This is all the more dangerous for being much less easily detected than in the case of newspapers. In this and in similar ways there have arisen in the train of the microforms a host of problems—problems relating to the physical and bibliographic standards which should govern their manufacture and processing; problems regarding the reading equipment necessary to their use (including the severe problem of private use by individuals in circumstances where expensive reading equipment is not readily available); problems relating to format and storage; legal problems, including those of copyright. Meanwhile, too, it has seemed to many that a form of copying which promised so much in terms of compression of space, cheapness of production, and exactitude of replication, has not realized its promise as might have been expected. It has not solved the space problems of libraries; it has not made it possible for individuals to compress well selected book collections into desk drawers; above all, it is difficult and unsatisfactory for many purposes of study.

To state the case thus is to do microforms an injustice. For their contribution has actually been enormous, and in a relatively short period. They have rescued many millions of pages of newspapers from oblivion at comparatively low cost and with a concomitant saving of

space. They have put within the reach of libraries of even moderate means, in exact facsimile, great segments of the important source literature of past ages which only a few of the greatest libraries could previously possess, and none even of them with the same completeness. They have made possible the assembly in convenient locations of vast quantities of research material on particular subjects whose originals are scattered in the libraries and archives of the world—beyond the means and reach of the average scholar, beyond the capacity for interlibrary lending. They have provided a major step toward the realization of the ideal of “one library.”

Outside of libraries, which actually form only about two per cent of the market for microcopying equipment and supplies, the microphotographic techniques have wide application to the records of business and engineering, and constitute a very considerable industry within which the development of equipment for making, processing, storing and using microcopies is continuous and elaborate. In this development, which is by no means confined to one or two countries, there is no dearth of intelligence, ingenuity, or capital. Even in the matter of standards, there are active committees at work in the several national standardizing organizations, and at the international level.

Under these circumstances, the question for the Council—to whose attention the problems of the use of the microforms in libraries had been brought even before its establishment—was where it might profitably intervene. To assist it in exploring this question and in accelerating its program in this area it convened in May 1958 **a meeting of representatives of both the users and the makers of microforms.** Among the recommendations made by the group was that the Council should simultaneously conduct research on a long range approach

and on a short range direct-amelioration program. It was also recommended that work should continue on development of equipment including microform readers of various types, and on an inexpensive step-and-repeat camera attachment for use with existing cameras; that publication in microform of standard reference and new material be encouraged; and that the Council promote the dissemination of information concerning characteristic devices, equipment and processes. The Council has pursued all of these recommendations and expects that implementing action may be taken early in the year ahead.

Devices for Exploitation of Microcopy

Even prior to the planning meeting just described, the Council had entered the field of microcopy problems. This first step was in the form of a contract with the Microcard Corporation for the development of an **improved hand reader**, primarily for micro-opaques (the varieties of microcopies reproduced on paper, card or other opaque material), but possibly also adaptable to the reading of the micro-transparencies (the forms typically reproduced on film).

The action was prompted by the reflection that the forms in which microcopy has been utilized in libraries have been chiefly borrowed from the commercial world where the emphasis has been on reduction of business and engineering records, and where the use of microcopied material is institutionalized and mechanized. Business in turn had borrowed the original format of the process from the motion picture industry. Thus, 35 mm. microfilm, normal in the cinema world, is still a widely accepted norm for microcopy; many of the variants—

8, 16, 70 and 105 mm. film—are but multiples or approximate sub-multiples of the original dimension. One of the consequences has been in the design of equipment for making use of the microcopy. Another is in the arrangement and ratio of reduction of the reproduced material, which is necessarily related to the dimensions of the film. Just as reading and writing in early Mesopotamia were controlled not by the reader's convenience but by the accident of clay as a material, so the application of microreproduction in libraries has been largely dictated by the accident of motion picture photography. Would it not be well to start from the reader's end and work the other way?

The question is easy enough to ask; it is not so easy to answer in concrete terms. Yet it seemed to the Council that a place to start was in making it more convenient for the individual private user to employ microtext in his studies without being dependent upon an expensive and institutionalized machine. One of the most effective devices for such private use was still rendered far from satisfactory by several defects: a comparatively high cost, a bothersome amount of instrumentation, and less-than-satisfactory optics. The last made it possible to read the microtext back at only three-fourths its original size and at the same time prevented the use of eye glasses. It was decided to attempt to improve this device by overcoming its defects and by simultaneously effecting a reduction in price. By the end of the year the first two defects mentioned had been overcome and improvement of the optics was so nearly within sight as to argue against immediate exploitation of the results. It is hoped, in consequence, that in the coming year an improved and inexpensive private reading device will be within realization.

ADMINISTRATIVE FACTORS

The media of bibliographic and of physical access possess, as has been seen, an enormous diversity of forms and applications. They range from the most general to the most special. When such of these mechanisms as are most appropriate for a particular purpose—whether to provide a selection of general reading matter for a small community or to collect comprehensively for research in some subject such as titanium metallurgy or Byzantine art—are housed in a building suitably equipped and operated by a staff suitably trained, a library occurs. The organization and administration of a library involves considerations which reach out into architecture and engineering, education, political science, public relations, personnel administration, testing and standardization, as well as legal considerations of many kinds. These factors all enter library work when libraries become institutions, and they may in consequence be called in general the operational or administrative factors. Like his opposite number in business or in industry, the librarian must be concerned to secure the best trained staff and to find the best form of organization to employ their abilities; like him he must discover the most efficient equipment and supplies in terms both of effectiveness and of cost if he is to be able to “sell” the best service at the lowest operational cost, which is his *raison d'être*.

Standardization and Testing

Perhaps more than his colleagues in business and industry, the librarian has been inattentive to and inexperienced in the use of standards, specifications and testing methods. This arises in part from the position of the library as consumer. It must for the most part

accept what the market affords. It does not itself constitute a purchasing area large enough or sufficiently well organized to affect, except in some signal instances such as library binding, what the market offers. As subordinate units of larger organizations such as universities, municipal governments, corporations or government departments, libraries must also often look for their procurement to purchasing agents quite ignorant of library needs. The result has too often been that price becomes the only criterion of procurement and there is no adequate regard to suitability.

The few areas in which generally adopted standards, and the facilities for policing these standards, have been brought into library work only emphasize the potentialities of improvement through further standardization. Library binding has already been mentioned as an area of successful and profitable standardization. This was a field in which librarians were able to work with an interested industry. Standards in cataloging have, of course, been basic to all important schemes of inter-library cooperation for a century. Standards in the fields of library training and library service have had similar importance. Most of the supplies, equipment and systems used by libraries, however, have not been similarly subjected to the testing which is a prerequisite both to the establishment and to the enforcement of standards. It is similarly true with respect to most aspects of building, equipment and supplies, and with respect to the very paper that makes up the book-stock, the processing of microfilm, the comparative efficiency of charging systems, and the like. There are relatively few standards and few ways in which the individual librarian can employ them.

This situation attracted the attention of the Council during its first year, and a staff paper attempted to

explore the possibility of developing a standardizing-testing program for library equipment, supplies and systems which might not only be of use but which might also — since testing is an expensive business — come within the economic feasibilities. A second step was taken during the year just past. A grant was made to the American Library Association to make an inquiry into the basis on which a continuing program for **testing-standardization** might be established by the Association. The inquiry, conducted by Mr. John H. Ottemiller, Associate Librarian of Yale University, is attempting to ascertain what standards relevant to library work now exist, what similarly relevant testing of products is now going on, and how these may be made available to librarians; what else needs to be done, and how it may be done and paid for by those who would benefit by it. Mr. Ottemiller, with the assistance of an advisory committee knowledgeable in the testing-standardization field, has been consulting with groups of librarians in various parts of the country in order to secure a precise estimate of the need and possible support for a testing program. His report is expected in the fall of 1959.

Training for Library Work

It is probable that the outstanding problem of library work at the moment, as viewed by librarians themselves, arises from difficulties in recruiting adequately trained staffs. The professional organizations of librarians are in consequence busy with recruitment campaigns. The Council has received numerous proposals for assisting these endeavors to bring capable people into library work, but has not as yet seen its way clear to do so. Though ignorance of the career possibilities of librarian-

ship may be an important factor contributing to the shortage of candidates, there are certainly other factors equally important, principal among which is the simple matter of the salaries offered to library school graduates with a master's degree as compared with those offered in other lines of work to those with a bachelor's degree. Nevertheless, the Council has been interested in approaching the recruitment problem if a promising line of inquiry should be found. In accordance with this interest, a small grant will make possible a meeting later this year of the **Committee on a Survey of Library Education** of the Joint Committee on Library Education of the Council of National Library Associations. This Committee will explore the relation between library education and library employment with a view to improving both.

An appropriate feature of the dedication of the new undergraduate library at the University of Michigan was a "**Conference on the Undergraduate and the Lifetime Reading Habit.**" As a contribution toward promotion of the use of library services, the Council gave support to the Conference, which explored the role of academic libraries in stimulating the cultivation of lifetime reading habits among undergraduates, assembled relevant information, and suggested courses of action. A report of the conference, held on the Ann Arbor campus in February 1958, is to be published by the University of Michigan Press.

FACT-FINDING AND PLANNING FOR RESEARCH

The Council's first annual report recorded its early recognition of the need for a review of the present "state of the art" in various aspects of library work which would serve to identify the problems and suggest avenues for profitable research. This recognition led to one of the Council's first grants. It was made to Rutgers University to enable Professor Ralph R. Shaw to organize a series of studies, to be conducted by a team, of some twenty-one areas of library work*. They will draw for the purpose not only on the published literature but also on unpublished evidence of practice. It was proposed that these studies, upon completion, would be submitted for discussion to panels of other experts in the field with a view to reaching a consensus as to **profitable targets for research in library work**. The studies have been under way during the past year and several have been completed. It is anticipated that all will be completed by March 1959, and publication is contemplated.

Several other grants were made during the year for projects of a fact-finding nature. One of these was to the American Library Association to draw together from the various sources in which they are now scattered—

* Authors and subjects include: Ralph Blasinghame, Jr., *Punched cards*; George Bonn, *Training of laymen in use of the library*; Margaret S. Bryant, *Bibliography*; Robert S. Collison, *Testing and standardization*; Ralph Ellsworth, *Buildings*; Carlyle Frarey, *Subject headings*; Helen Harrar, *Cooperative acquisition*; William Hawken, *Full-size photographic processes*; Reginald Hawkins, *Production of microforms*; Doralyn J. Hickey, *Mechanical reproduction of codes in Yes-No Form*; Louis Kaplan, *Storage of library materials*; Lila Kirkwood, *Charging systems*; Jerrold Orne, *Storage warehouses*; Felix Reichmann, *Notched cards*; Jesse Shera, *Education for librarianship*; Jean Stewart, *Reading devices for micro-images*; Maurice Tauber, *Cataloging and classification*; Donald Thompson, *Gifts and exchanges*; Lawrence Thompson, *Peek-a-boo systems*; M. Voight and Gerald Jahoda, *Electronic devices*; and Edith C. Wise, *Classification systems*.

the United States Office of Education, the library agencies of the various states, and from individual libraries which have not as yet reported to any central agency—the facts of library service in the United States. The present situation is one which presents large gaps of knowledge for the reason that a concomitant of inadequacy is failure to report. While it is easy, in consequence, to ascertain what the major public library systems and great university libraries expend, it is not known how many degree-giving institutions do not possess even an up-to-date encyclopedia. The principal study is being made by Mr. Ralph M. Dunbar, recently retired chief of the Library Services Division of the Office of Education. Meanwhile, however, the Association has commissioned and published three pamphlets calling attention to the situation: *Every Child Needs a School Library*, by Miss Mary Virginia Gaver; *Books and Libraries: Tools of the Academic World*, by Dr. Flora B. Ludington, and *Fountains Not Reservoirs: The Public Library*, by Mr. Arthur H. Parsons, Jr.

Another fact-finding inquiry has concerned **libraries in the Soviet Union**. With the recent renewal of cultural exchanges between the United States and Russia, many American visitors have made inquiries about and in Soviet libraries which have been misdirected or futile because of lack of prior understanding of the Soviet system of library and bibliographic organization. It appeared useful to commission a study which would describe this organization, thus enabling future visitors to pursue their inquiries more efficiently. Such a study has been prepared by Dr. Paul L. Horecky and Mr. Boris I. Gorokhoff, members of the staff of the Slavic Division, Library of Congress, with the editorial advice of Dr. Sergius Yakobson, chief of the division. Plans for publication are now in progress.

To explore avenues toward the solution of the **problems of libraries in institutions of higher learning**, the Council gave support to a first meeting of a joint committee of the Association of American Colleges and of the Association of College and Research Libraries. The meeting, held March 28-29, 1958, examined a number of topics of common interest and provided for further study of some of these through appointment of committees. Work has in consequence continued and shows promise of bearing fruit.

The International Federation of Library Associations was established, with active American participation, in 1929. The Federation provides an international forum for discussion and joint effort, but does not have revenue sufficient to maintain an active secretariat. Its members, prevented by distance from more than occasional meetings, find it difficult to pursue active programs of development. The organization therefore does not occupy the position of effectiveness which it potentially can and desirably might occupy. Believing that a minimum program can be devised which may more effectively than now involve the collaboration of the far-flung membership, the Council commissioned a study of this program by Mr. Edward J. Carter, a British subject who was until recently head of the Libraries Division of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, which has been desirous of finding a strong international, non-governmental organization in the field of library work.

A landmark in the exploration of problems of scientific communication, both in and out of libraries, was the Royal Society of London's Scientific Information Conference in 1948. In the decade that has elapsed the problems of both scientific and other communication have been aggravated by the continued acceleration in

the rate of publication. There has been much discussion and experimentation, and some real progress toward solutions. The time has seemed ripe for a re-survey of the situation in an international meeting which would bring together representatives of the same groups which had an interest in the problems in 1948 and in addition those which have since entered the picture—mathematicians, statisticians, linguists, groups working with computers and other data processing machines and other allied groups. To this end the National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council, National Science Foundation and American Documentation Institute have sponsored a week-long **International Conference on Scientific Information** to be held in Washington in November 1958. In the belief that such a conference holds much promise for future developments in this area through exchange of views between specialists who otherwise have little occasion to communicate with each other and by stimulation of research in the field, the Council has contributed toward defraying the cost of the conference.

Toward the end of its second year the Council began to review its program policy in the light of its activities and of the various proposals made to it up to that time. To aid in this consideration it convened in May a panel of distinguished persons representing a wide diversity of learned activities to take a look at **the Council's program** as so far conducted and to advise as to its future direction. The Council has subsequently drafted a restatement of its program policy which remains for final adoption in the coming year. The members of the panel included: Julian P. Boyd, Editor, *The Papers of Thomas Jefferson*; Paul H. Buck, Director of Libraries, Harvard University; Leonard Carmichael, Secretary, Smithsonian Institution; David H. Clift, Executive Secretary, American Library Association; Fred Cole, Vice

President, Tulane University; Donald Coney, Director of Libraries, University of California; H. Bentley Glass, Professor of Biology, Johns Hopkins University; Philip M. Morse, Director of the Computation Center, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, and L. Quincy Mumford, Librarian of Congress.

CONCLUSION

In reviewing the fiscal year 1958, it becomes evident that the library world parallels the larger world, a larger world ever growing smaller. What may be done in Lübeck or London will have its effect on the catalogs of Stanford and Harvard; and the techniques of photography—and perhaps someday those of telefacsimile also—promise to reduce the barriers to inquiry by strides as great as did the invention of printing from movable type five hundred years ago. The improvement of the mechanisms used by libraries is not to be dreaded as the encroachment of the machine upon intellectual work. Just as the printing press, the card catalog, the pneumatic tube and the book carrier have contributed to the liberation rather than the limitations of the mind's inquiry, so too may other mechanical devices, even automata, serve the same end. But not by themselves. All mechanisms are but tools, extensions of the body's or the mind's reach; and in library work their improvement must reflect improvement in preparation for the work through training, or organization, or cooperation. Only so may these mechanisms be expected to bring closer the day when the resources of the world's libraries may constitute "one library" to which all may have access, wherever they may be.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

F I N A N C I A L S T A T E M E N T S

Accountant's Opinion

AUGUST 7, 1958

TO THE BOARD OF DIRECTORS OF
COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1958 and the expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of such statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards, and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

JUNE 30, 1958

ASSETS

Cash	\$ 147,601
Investments, at cost (approximate market):	
Federal National Mortgage Association bonds, 4% % due July 1958	301,500
Twelve Federal Land Banks Consolidated Federal Farm Loans bonds, 2¼% due November 1958	198,375
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (collectible \$1,250,000 annually to June 30, 1961).....	3,750,000
Accrued interest receivable and deposits	12,530
	\$4,410,006

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and research contracts payable, per accompanying statement	\$ 167,587
Accounts payable and accrued salaries	3,464
Fund balance:	
Balance June 30, 1957	\$4,730,663
Expenditures less income for the year.....	491,708
	4,238,955
	\$4,410,006

**STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES
AND INCOME
FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1958**

EXPENDITURES:

Grants, research contracts and Council-administered projects, per accompanying statement		\$403,361
General administrative expense—		
Compensation and employee benefits	\$78,064	
Rent	6,402	
Professional services	2,702	
Furniture and equipment	2,272	
Travel and meetings	6,574	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	9,187	105,201
		508,562
INCOME		
From investments		16,854
Expenditures less income		\$491,708

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, RESEARCH CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL - ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year ended June 30, 1958

	Payable June 30, 1957	Total grant or contract	Payments in 1957-1958	Payable June 30, 1958
American Historical Association				
Compilation of a Guide to Photographed Historical Materials Available for Research in Libraries and Archives in the United States and Canada		\$58,100	\$30,100	\$28,000
American Library Association				
Analysis and report of the Southwest Missouri Library Service cooperative processing center demonstration		1,000	1,000	
Library resources fact-finding survey		12,125	12,125	
"Library Technology": A feasibility study.....		14,944	14,944	
Towards the international coordination of cataloging rules*		(227)	(227)	
Travel grants to promote the international coordination of cataloging rules		5,000	5,000	
Edward J. Carter				
Report on basis for more effective participation of the American library world in International Federation of Library Associations		500	500	
Committee on a Survey of Library Education of the Joint Committee on Library Education of the Council of National Library Associations				
To defray expenses of a meeting of the Committee†		1,000		1,000
The deFlorez Company, Inc.				
Design plan for an automatic book-cradle/page-turner		5,000		5,000
W. C. Huebner				
A demonstration model of "Migrafax"		2,000	2,000	
International Federation of Library Associations				
For a preliminary meeting on the international coordination of cataloging rules		19,995		19,995
Joint Committee of the Association of American Colleges and Association of College and Research Libraries				
To defray expenses of a meeting of the Committee†		694	694	
Harry J. Krould				
A report on the bases for regional coordination of library reference services		9,400	4,800	4,600
Library of Congress				
Demonstration and evaluation of "cataloging in source"		55,000	55,000	

	Payable June 30, 1957	Total grant or contract	Payments in 1957-1958	Payable June 30, 1958
Exploration of next steps towards an international cataloging code		314	314	
Feasibility study of "cataloging in source".....		2,822	2,822	
Meeting on the problems of microform in libraries†		1,683	1,683	
Meeting of Advisory Panel to Review the Council's program†		\$1,868	\$1,868	
The Microcard Corporation				
Development of improved hand-reading devices for micro-opaques		11,750	6,000	\$5,750
National Academy of Sciences—National Research Council				
Towards the expenses of the International Conference on Scientific Information.....		15,000	15,000	
National Library of Medicine				
Improvement of bibliographic compilation through mechanization, with specific application to the Current List of Medical Literature		73,800	47,300	26,500
Princeton University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries)				
Survey and evaluation of the Farmington Plan		21,000	21,000	
Radio Corporation of America				
Design plan for a "cataloger's camera".....		3,000	3,000	
Design plan for an automatic book-cradle/page-turner		5,000		5,000
Feasibility model of a "cataloger's camera".....		22,789		22,789
Rutgers University, Graduate School of Library Service				
"Targets for Research in Library Work".....	\$87,500		50,000	37,500
Nasser Sharify				
Towards a cataloging code for Persian materials (2 grants)		8,966	8,966	
Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.				
Assistance in demonstration of cooperative centralized processing for public libraries		4,000	4,000	
The United States Book Exchange, Inc.				
The United States Book Exchange: A re-evaluation of its operations		16,131	16,131	
University of Michigan				
Feasibility study of "Telereference"		14,850	8,147	6,703
Toward expenses of the National Conference on the Undergraduate and the Lifetime Reading Habit		5,000	5,000	
Virginia State Library				
Deterioration of book-stock—causes and remedies	33,000		33,000	
Sergius Yakobson, Boris I. Gorokhoff and Paul L. Horecky				
Preparation of a report on libraries in the information-dissemination process in the Soviet Union (2 contracts)		10,857	6,107	4,750
Total	\$120,500	\$403,361	\$356,274	\$167,587

* Refund of portion of grant awarded in prior year

† Council-administered project

TRI

ents

R

... now planning ex-
ploit... famous boost
of the French Air
... leads a
... Europe
... rate

APHY

by 2 55

$$\left(1 + \frac{87}{d_1}\right)$$

Leesville
Batesburg
Ridge Spring
Went

1938 37
1940 34
1949 33
1953 33
1958 33

1938 33
1940 33
1949 33
1953 33
1958 33

